

CONFLUENCE MIXING: SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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This document contains supporting information for a planned research project “Confluence mixing: near-field hydrodynamic controls of the intermodal behavior and their implications for fish ecology (CofeMix+)” by Alexander Sukhodolov, Christian Wolter and Quinn Lewis (DFG SU-405/11).

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Relation of the proposed research to our preliminary studies.

Preliminary field-based and analytical research of our team has focused on studying two generic classes of flows: mixing/shear layers and wakes and the interactions of these flows in shallow concordant confluences (Sukhodolov & Sukhodolova 2019; Sukhodolov et al. 2023), Fig. S5. We have examined how two initially quasi-uniform shallow flows mix and interact together to form patterns in the post-confluence channel. We demonstrated the importance of the wake forming next to the confluence apex due to flow stagnation and the necessity to account for lateral advective fluxes of momentum generated by the secondary helical flow due to imbalance between centrifugal and gravity forces.

In the proposed research we will expand this analytical framework by introducing more general solutions for confluence mixing that will account for a strong jet effect. Fig. S6 demonstrates a decomposition scheme in which the total velocity difference ΔU inside the mixing interface is the sum of fractional contributions of mixing-layer ϕ_m , wake ϕ_w and jet ϕ_j , $\phi_m + \phi_w + \phi_j = 1$. We anticipate that a jet forms when a local excess of streamwise momentum appears due to gravity, continuity or interactions of flows within apex. Inclusion of jet effect into multi-modal behavior will allow modeling riverbed discordance and local flow non-uniformity due to river regulation, Fig. S6. Strong gravitational effects are expected when joining riverbeds are accomplished by larger slopes of tributaries compared to main rivers, which normally occupy the lower and flat areas within river networks (Sukhodolov et al. 2017). A similar effect can be imposed when one of the

Fig. S5 (a-c) Patterns of mixing in the experiments with shallow mixing layers (a), shallow wakes (b) and 40° confluence model (c). (d-f) Lateral profiles of streamwise velocity for junction flows with asymptotic behavior for mixing layer (d) and wake (f). (h) Lateral profiles of streamwise velocity at a shallow confluence composed of mixing layer and wake fractions. (e-i) Measured (symbols) and modeled dynamics of mixing interface width corresponding to patterns (a-c).

Fig. S6 Lateral profiles of streamwise velocity and corresponding patterns of mixing at river confluences. (a) In mixing-layer mode with strong wake effect (preliminary research). (b) Behavior which is expected in mixing-layer mode with strong jet effect (proposed research). (c) An example with dominant wake mode at the Danube and Siret Rivers confluence (45°24'14"N 28°01'30"E, dashed line shows the boundary of stagnation zone and arrows highlight shed vortices in the wake, source GoogleEarth). (d) The Oder and Bobr Rivers confluence in the mixing-layer mode with a strong jet effect (52°02'59"N 15°04'19"E dashed line highlights the core of a jet, source GoogleEarth).

joining channels of nearly equal riverbed slope has planar constriction (narrowing) close to the junction to meet the continuity requirement, Fig. S6d. The constriction of the flow domain can also happen due to deflection of the flow caused by interactions with a joining stream. In our schematization we hypothesize that the effect of jetting can be superimposed on the uniform flow condition for the tributary channel, which, in the absence of additional forcing, will normally lead to a mixing interface either with a strong mixing-layer or strong wake effect, Fig. S6a. Prof. Constantinescu, a proposed Mercator Fellow for this project, has provided pilot DES results illustrating the jet effect in a shallow discordant confluence, which support our expectations for the proposed schematization as a realistic scenario, Fig. S7.

Fig. S7 Pilot DES simulations of a shallow discordant confluence with a strong jet effect. (a) Instant patterns of flow vorticity at the free surface (the pattern shows the jet core at the mouth of tributary flanked by shear layers on both sides producing large-scale structures in the far field). (b) Mean velocity at the centerline of the jet.

Field sites of the proposed case studies. The LSB confluence hydrodynamics was examined in our previous research combining field measurements with numerical simulations (Sukhodolov et

al. 2017), Fig. 8a. This is a discordant confluence with the junction angle of 65° and a bed discordance factor of 38%. The hydrodynamics of LSB mixing interface is characterized by the presence of a jet evolving similar to a free asymmetric jet. However, numerical simulations suggested that for some specific flow conditions (e.g., increased flow shallowness) the jet flow can change to a riverbed attached jet (Sukhodolov et al. 2017). In addition, morphodynamical changes at the confluence modify the stagnation zone and the separation zone characteristics including vegetation effects. The field site is already equipped with permanent geodetical marks allowing referencing on the previous local coordinate system. Because the LSB confluence is a popular hotspot for local anglers, it will be also important to document their activities with a trail camera and by performing questioner-based survey about fish catches.

Fig. S8 Field sites of case studies at the Tagliamento River (MP-TAG), images taken with UAVs. (a) Discordant confluence of the Ledra River with the Torrente Sorgive die Bars (LSB) with mixing with a strong jet effect. (b) An example of a junction with steep avalanche faces at a braided floodplain of the Tagliamento River (two free surface jets collide and form a pressure wave in the middle).

The TF confluence is a morphodynamically dynamic confluence because of the braided style of both the Tagliamento and Fella Rivers, Fig. 1a. The junction angle of TF confluence can vary depending on the water level and topography. Thereby, monitoring this confluence can provide a variety of relevant conditions including concordant and discordant cases, Fig. 8b. The distance between LSB and TF field sites is about 20 km, which allows monitoring and remote sensing to be performed during the same day. Contrasts in water turbidity are almost always present on the LSB confluence. At the TF confluence, the contrast in the color of water can be almost always distinguished because of different mineral composition of dissolved substances.

Fig. S9 Field sites of case studies at the Oder River (MP-ODW-N) (images from GoogleEarth). Confluence of the rivers Oder and Warthe (ODW); (a) Low flow with strong topographical steering from the sand bars and groynes, (b) Intermediate flow in a mixing-layer mode. (c) High flow with mixing in a wake mode; Confluence of the rivers Oder and Neiße (ODN); (d) Low flow with strong effect of a groyne field (mixing recirculation flow forcing effect); (e) Intermediate flow when mixing dynamics are in wake mode due to forcing induced by groynes; and (f) High flow with mixing in a wake mode. The apex of the confluence becomes inundated and the effect of riparian vegetation on the floodplain of the apex strongly affects the wake dynamics.

Fig. S10 An example of a natural river confluence with a strong effect of recirculation forcing, confluence of the Colorado River with the Havasu Creek in the Grand Canyon. (a,d) Low flow with mixing in a wake mode. (b,e) Intermediate flow, with mixing in wake mode and the recirculation forcing. (c,f) High flow with mixing subject to strong effects due to recirculation forcing and jetting (insert in f illustrates strong density current at the mixing interface due to strong differences in turbidity).

Fig. S11 A scheme of confluence apex shapes and configurations. (a) Apex with the banks orthogonal to the riverbed with triangular and rounded shapes (dashed lines indicate hypothetical separation lines and first vortex rolls). (b) Apex with banks at 30° angle with respect to the riverbed. (c) With patches of vegetation.

Fig. S11 Dynamics of chlorophyll concentration along the Oder River (data derived from satellite remotely sensed images).

Characteristics of planned field-based experiments

Table S1 Characteristics of planned field-based experiments (FC-1).

Run	θ	D_r (%)	ϑ	M_r	U_r	Q (m ³ s ⁻¹)	B (m)	H (m)	A (m ²)	U (ms ⁻¹)
Concordant riverbeds										
1	40°	0	0°	0.85	1.2	0.5	3.0	0.40	1.2	0.42
						0.7	5.0	0.40	2.0	0.35
2	40°	0	0°	0.60	1.7	0.6	3.0	0.40	1.2	0.50
						0.6	5.0	0.40	2.0	0.30
3	40°	0	0°	0.40	2.4	0.7	3.0	0.40	1.2	0.60
						0.5	5.0	0.40	2.0	0.25
Discordant riverbeds										
4	40°	35	90°	0.40	2.7	0.6	3.0	0.25	0.75	0.80
						0.6	5.0	0.40	2.0	0.30
5	40°	35	30°	0.40	2.7	0.6	3.0	0.25	0.75	0.80
						0.6	5.0	0.40	2.0	0.30

Note. θ is the junction angle, D_r is the discordance ratio, ϑ is the angle of discordant riverbed, M_r is the momentum flux ratio, U_r is the velocity ratio, Q is the discharge, H is the mean flow depth, A is the area of cross section, U is the mean flow velocity. For each experimental run, values in the upper and lower strings represent tributary and main river, respectively.

Table S2 Characteristics of planned field-based experiments (FC-2).

Run	θ	γ	Θ	Υ	M_r	U_r	Q (m ³ s ⁻¹)	B (m)	H (m)	A (m ²)	U (ms ⁻¹)
Free stagnation zone											
1	40°	90°	triangle	-	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31
2	40°	30°	triangle	-	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31
3	40°	90°	round	-	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31
4	40°	30°	round	-	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31
Vegetated stagnation zone											
5	40°	30°	round	Rigid	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31
6	40°	30°	round	Flexible	2.0	1.4	0.7	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.43
							0.5	4.0	0.40	1.6	0.31

Note. γ is the bank sloping angle (90° corresponds to vertical wall), Θ is the shape factor, Υ is the vegetation type.

Annex 1. Occasion-related special investigation program on the environmental disaster in the River Oder from August 2022 – ODER~SO

ODER~SO is a collaborative project on damage to aquatic organisms, regeneration of the biocenoses, precautionary studies in relation to possible further prymnesin-poisoning, as well as resilience, ecosystem services and deriving proposals for action to protect floodplains. The project is financed by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV).

After the catastrophic event in August 2023 the following research needs have been identified:

1) **Losses of aquatic biota** have so far been partially quantified only for fish and molluscs, but are still unknown for other organism groups. Recovery of populations of all organism groups is expected, but remains uncertain, since the River Oder is still heavily polluted and after the mass kill of many species, invasive species might now occupy vacant niches in the ecosystem.

Since chemical water quality is a critical factor in the mass development of the toxic alga *Prymnesium parvum*, supplementary monitoring of water chemistry and ecological parameters and their analysis is required. To determine effects of *Prymnesium parvum* on different animal groups and species, the nature and type of interaction of the algae and the toxin with the damaged biota needs to be investigated, as well as the concentration-dependent effects of the two factors. An eDNA-based multitrophic monitoring can fully map the population dynamics of all groups of aquatic organisms including microscopic organisms that are not captured in traditional monitoring, but form the basis for the higher trophic levels.

2) **Establishing predictive bases and early warning tools:** further elucidation of the causal chain of toxin production and algal damage effects is needed to enable improved assessment of the likelihood of recurrence of such a disaster, as well as improved possibilities for prognosis and prevention. Because of the dimension of the River Oder disaster, this requires a spatio-temporal analysis of the multi-causal development and spread of algal blooms in this river system, to identify the interaction between climate change and water pollution as the main causal factors and thus to provide the foundation for longer warning times in the future. The development of a DNA chip allows a timely as well as cost- and time-saving detection of *Prymnesium*.

3) The **self-regulatory functions** of the ecosystem are reduced to an unknown extent as a result of the loss of previously only partially known parts of the biocoenosis to an unknown extent. This includes the filtration capacity of filter-feeding animals and microorganisms with respect to suspended algae, whose reduction will have an unknown effect on the coming growth periods of the phytoplankton. Since apparently also parts of the bottom-dwelling invertebrate fauna (macrozoobenthos) are affected, the degradation of coarse particulate organic material (fallen leaves, rooted aquatic plants, detritus) may be similarly affected.

4) The **refugial function of floodplain** waters has been shown to be significant for the survival of many fish and aquatic invertebrates. Therefore, the biocoenotic floodplain condition of the River Oder floodplain and the role of floodplain waters as refugia for fish and aquatic invertebrates will be investigated. The resilience of individual species to *Prymnesium* is also largely unknown, but is significant for estimating the consequences of further algal blooms, and which may also lead to the identification of protective mechanisms.

5) The effects of **human impacts**, including climate change, on the river floodplain ecosystem and the **ecosystem services** available there, which are also the economic basis of fisheries and tourism enterprises along the River Oder will be significantly affected by intensifying the engineering works and uses of the river and floodplain. The reduction of all impacts and

targeted renaturation can contribute to increase resilience of the river and floodplain system. Therefore, three future scenarios will be modelled to predict the water storage function of the floodplains, their function as habitat and biodiversity hotspot as well as the ecosystem services including nutrient retention and carbon sequestration.

Based on this functional background, the **ODER-SO project aims** for the following objectives:

- A) Monitoring and analysis of algal and contaminant loads
- B) Documentation of remaining populations of key aquatic organism groups
- C) Documentation of the regeneration of populations of important aquatic organism groups
- D) Toxin precautionary studies related to potential further prymnesine poisoning.
- E) Depiction of floodplain resilience, refugial functions and ecosystem services under three development scenarios.

In total 13 subprojects will cover all urgent investigation needs regarding the River Oder catastrophe. Subproject 11 “Fish ecological impacts and recovery of the River Oder” will particularly complement this research proposal, Fig.1. It aims in assessing the recovery potential of the fish assemblage. Special objectives are:

- 1) Determining current, species-specific population declines compared to time series of fish densities since 1998
- 2) Assessing fish stock recovery, especially of juvenile fish abundance and immigration
- 3) comparative investigation of the refugial function of permanently and temporarily connected floodplain waters for fish

To achieve these targets the subproject performs extensive habitat specific fish samplings for adult and juvenile fish along all major river sections, tributaries, and functional floodplain waters. These fish data will feed into the proposed project to address the questions on the degree of river regulation and their implications for fish (Q-1), how fish is using stagnation zones as a habitat (Q-2) and which mixing processes are critical for fish populations in river networks (Q-3).

Fig. 1. The structure of the ODER-SO project.

Annex 2. Agent-based pattern-oriented modeling of fish population survival during a passage of a dissolved toxin nearby a confluence in a river trained with groynes.

Motivation During the last four decades individual-based modeling of fish populations has become a helpful tool in understanding complex ecological phenomena including fish migrations, schooling and assessing risk of fish mortality due to elevated chemical loads (Grimm et al. 2005; 2017). The workflow of this modeling includes (1) compiling information at the lower level of the system, (2) formulating theories about their behavior, (3) implementing the theories in computer simulations, and (4) examining the emergence of system properties (Grimm et al. 2005). Pattern-oriented modeling (POM) approaches are methods that attempt to increase structural realism in modeling of complex systems where the dynamics are impossible to formulate in terms of analytical equations. For example, a group of adult fish within a river reach cannot be represented as a continuum and its dynamics would be impossible to examine in terms of fluxes in a way similar to fluxes of physical quantities such as momentum. However, fish-flow interactions can be described as a balance of forces which defines the spatial patterns and trajectories of fish.

For fish within the river reach close to confluence the formulation of goals governing their foraging behavior can be more straightforward as their location can be directly related to the source of prey located at the tributary and can thus be approximated by regularly repeated (e.g. patrol-like) trajectories between stagnant and fast flowing areas. Predation-avoiding behavior to avoid predation can be related either to positioning in the turbid water or deeper areas (e.g. confluence scour holes, back refuges, aquatic vegetation).

Our previous research has already established the background for the development of the model by compiling the information about physical processes that can be formulated in terms of patterns. This is due to the development of quantitative theories for confluence dynamics and mixing (Sukhodolov et al. 2023), transport and mixing of contaminants in regulated rivers (Czernuszenko et al. 1998), exchange processes between main river and groyne fields (Sukhodolov 2014), and individual-based modeling of algae in groyne fields (Engelhardt et al. 2004). These theories have already produced analytical solutions with parameters of mainly universal character and therefore they are straightforward to incorporate into computer code. These kinds of models are free of numerical uncertainties and usually computationally inexpensive due to minimization of iterative computations. The development of the agent-based modeling will be supported by our ongoing research of flow-fish interactions based on video records of fish trajectories in natural rivers.

Modeling of flow and spread of toxins The confluence river reaches, which will be of the primary interest for our AB modeling and ODER-SO data interpretation, are Y-shaped shallow ($B/H \approx 100$) confluences. They are very similar to those examined in our field-based experiments (Sukhodolov et al. 2023), Fig. 1. The flow fields define the balance of forces acting on a fish and mixing processes within and downstream the confluences and also characterize flow exchange between the main river flow and groyne fields. The spread of toxins in the main river upstream of the confluence can be modeled using a one dimensional longitudinal dispersion model with dead zones (Czernuszenko et al. 1998). Fig. 2a illustrates the effect of a dead zone's relative volume ε and mean residence time T on the spread of pollutants from an instantaneous injection. This

Fig. 1 Measured flow velocities and their analytical modeling (lower panel) with combined exponential-hyperbolic tangent function (a). Spatial patterns of turbulent lateral fluxes of momentum (upper panel) and their analytical modeling (b). Spread and mixing of dissolved substance (upper panel) and modeling of mixing interface by intermodal theory (c).

Fig. 2 The concentration curves downstream of instantaneous injection modeled with longitudinal dispersion model with dead zones (a). Decrease of concentration in a groyne field after the passage of the contamination cloud (b).

model will produce upstream boundary conditions to simulate the propagation of a toxin cloud. Downstream of the confluence apex the hybrid 2-D model will be used combining a one dimensional longitudinal dispersion model with dead zones with the mixing interface model based on intermodal behavior. Modeling of mixing within groyne fields and groyne field sequences will be based on the aspect ratio criteria for the mean flow structure (Sukhodolov et al. 2002), Fig. 3a,b. While the relative volume of dead zones produced by groyne fields can be estimated from the simple geometrical calculations, the estimates of residence time will be made using the scaling relations based on the Richardson-Obukhov scaling law for the mixing interface between the main flow and groyne fields (Constantinescu et al. 2009), Fig. 3c.

Fig. 3 (a) Effect of aspect ratio (width to length) on the recirculation patterns of flow inside groyne fields (Sukhodolov et al. 2002). (b) Flow velocity patterns measured in the field experiments with groyne fields confirming criteria of the aspect ratio (Sukhodolov 2014). (c) Comparison of scaled characteristic phases of groyne field mixing in the field experiments and numerical modeling (Constantinescu et al 2009).

Modeling of fish trajectories in the river flow Fish will be modeled as a single solid object moving in the water according to the forces balanced in the medium (i.e. water flow), though

avoiding collisions with the solid boundaries. We will focus on planar, 2-dimensional motion assuming that the flow is shallow and well mixed over the local flow depth. The equations of motion for the fish will be represented by ordinary differential equations

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = U_i, \quad \frac{dU_i}{dt} = A_i, \quad U_i = u_{w,i} - u_{f,i}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

where A is the acceleration, U is the velocity, t is time, u_w is water velocity, u_f is fish velocity, x is the coordinate. The accelerations are affected by the flow velocities and fish behavior. Spatial patterns of flow velocities and toxin concentration will be provided by the hydrodynamic and mixing models for each point of computational grid and each moment of time. We assume that a fish moves in the water by producing thrust P , while water exerts drag force D on a fish due to skin friction D_s and form drag D_p as

$$D = D_s + D_p = 0.5 \rho (C_f S_a + C_p S_p) U^2, \quad (2)$$

where C_f and C_p are drag coefficients for skin and form drag, respectively, S_a is surface area of the fish body, and S_p is projected area of fish. Thrust is defined by the specific mode of swimming. Conventionally, three modes are defined: sustained, prolonged and burst (Wolter & Arlinghaus 2003). These conventional modes are suitable for modeling of large-scale processes (e.g. migrations). At the local scale related to confluences, fish motions to hold the position and to arrange patrolling motion at the edge of wake formed by stagnation zone will require different modeling, which will involve (1) interaction with turbulent vortices by changing projected area by body bending and engaging fins (e.g. karman gaiting); and (2) involving gliding when mean flow exerts a side-slip component in a cross flow, Fig. 4. Thrust can be parametrized as a squared fish velocity with a total drag coefficient. Fish velocity is species-specific and depends on the allometric relations (Videler 1993; Wolter & Arlinghaus 2003). To calculate thrust in position holding mode we will use the turbulent velocity that can be obtained for large-scale motions using a model of turbulent spectra for wake or mixing layer mode. To calculate glide the projection of flow velocity, the side slip component of velocity vector, will be used as a characteristic velocity.

Fig. 4 (a) An example of feeding behavior at the mixing interface in wake mode (black dashed line is motion in karman gait mode; red dashed line is in the burst mode to switch between eddies). (b) An example of ferry-gliding across a jet flow (yellow dashed line shows the motion in gliding mode, blue triangle is potential core of a jet).

We will not attempt to provide a detailed physiological model to calculate the energy costs because we will focus on the relatively small-scale motions performed within the habitat familiar to fish. Instead, we will focus on the effects of toxins that can accumulate in the fish tissue and will reduce its swimming performance. This will be implemented as an internal “stopwatch” W , which a maximum is set based on the mass of fish body m . The time is reduced according to the time the fish spends in the toxic water T_r as

$$\frac{dW}{dt} = -f(m, T_r) \quad (3)$$

When the amount of W is reduced to zero, the fish is assumed to be dead.

Therefore, the fish model will be represented by the following set of equations

$$\frac{du_{f,i}}{dt} = 0.5 \rho (C_f S_a + C_p S_p) \frac{U_f^2}{m} + \frac{P_i}{m} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dx_j}{dt} = u_{f,i} \quad (5)$$

Ordinary differential equations (3)-(5) will be solved simultaneously numerically by applying a fourth-order Runge-Kutta method using data about flow and toxin concentration from the spatial-temporal grid representing the computational domain.

Model parameterization and verification In this study we will use the results of previous work on the physical aspects of swimming such allometric relations, swimming performance for different fish species, and the data about skin and form drag which are also the topic of intensive ongoing research with RIBES ITN EU project. For parameterization and verification, we will use data also collected in the RIBES project. Fig. 5 illustrates some typical examples of observations of fish behavior in a flow with jet-like structure and recirculation wakes. These observations allow accurate digitalization of fish trajectories, fish size, body orientation and determination of fish velocity by subtracting the measured flow velocity. These are unique data, which to our knowledge, are not available from the literature for natural environments. The studies of fish intoxication in the frame of ongoing ODER-SO project will allow us also to parameterize the process of fish intoxication and mortality.

Fig. 5 (a) A view of the experimental reach on the Arzino River in Italy. Red circles indicate locations of geo-referencing marks M_1 and M_2 which are visible on the frames and provide the coordinates for digitalization of fish trajectories. Inset shows the distribution of mean streamwise velocity in a cross-section through the middle of a white rectangle that shows the enlarged area. **(b)** Trajectory of an individual fish superimposed for 6 different moments of time when fish performs a gliding motion across the jet (yellow dashed line shows the trajectory of fish head and white arrows indicate the view of the underwater camera). **(c)** Three frames from an underwater camera superimposed.

Simulations The simulations with the AB model will consist of several scenarios in which many individual fish will be initially placed at different locations around the numerical confluence domain. Thus, the first set will explore the situation when the toxin cloud arrives during the time when fish are feeding at the mixing interface. In this scenario we anticipate the greatest chances for fish to survive because of their initial proximity to unpolluted water. Predation-avoiding behavior during feeding will be another scenario, which might increase the mortality due to more intensive use of polluted water in the main river. A predator can be introduced as a larger fish with a goal to detect the prey visually and attack, though the success can be modeled with a certain probability function. Another dangerous scenario will be when fish are in the strong predation-avoiding mode scenario and are located in the different stagnant waters as for example in the groyne fields. Although the incomplete mixing between the main river and groyne fields can protect the fish, it is not clear how it might work on prolonged passage of the contaminants. As the result of simulations, we will obtain information on survival rates, their spatial distributions and the information about the factors that increased/decreased the survival rates. This information will be

compared to the results of surveys performed in the ODER-SO program and will support the interpretation of the obtained results.

Computer code In this project we will further extend our in-house code, which was first developed to support interpretation of data from field surveys of algae spread in the Elbe River (Engelhard et al. 2004). This is completely object-oriented code designed and developed in C++ by A. Sukhodolov, who has professional experience with developing commercial applications for Nortek AS, Norway (ExploreV, 1998). The early version of the software focused on the particles passively transported in the turbulent flow. Fig. 2b illustrates the results of simulations with the code for the flushing of the groyne field area after initially uniform distribution of algae. This code is currently being upgraded to simulate fish behavior in jet-like flows (e.g. transitions at riffle-pool sequences in the frame of RIBES project). The code is supplied with detailed documentation and is planned to be freely-shared software, which can also support the applications of remotely-sensing methods of mixing assessment.

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Annex 3. Field Experimental Facilities and Setup

The experimental facility of the proposed study is an in-stream flume with two inlet tributary sections (Fig. 1a). Two needle weirs will be constructed at the entrance to regulate the flow rates (item 1, Fig. 1a). The prototype of this facility comes from our previous field experimental study on river confluences, *Sukhodolov & Sukhodolova* (2016), and shown in Fig. 1c. The walls of the flume will be assembled of 1.5×0.5×0.25 m box-cages, which are manufactured from wooden bars, metal mesh and a plastic cover (*Sukhodolov* 2016). The box-cages will be filled with gravel and will create stable impermeable structures. With the needle weir in the front of the facility, the flow in the experimental open-channel can be accurately adjusted to desirable values. However, because the box cages are manufactured from inexpensive materials and wooden frames, they decay in harsh environments and can be used only during a single season. This is why we cannot reuse the materials from the previous study and the box-cages need to be manufactured again. The design of the confluence apex will also be different and will gradually lead the approach flow into tributary sections, eliminating any hydraulic effects of the entrance flow structure. This design was created based on experience with previous confluence models that required some adjustments directly in the field.

In the previous study we used a flat frame measurement setup and a floatable bridge (Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d). Although those setups have served the purposes of the studies well, they both had disadvantages because they required complete disassembling/assembling when the setup was moved between the cross-sections. In addition, the bridge setup was quite heavy because of the use of steel to manufacture the float. Those floats also cannot be removed during the studies. In the proposed research we plan to carry out more than twice as many experimental runs and it will be only possible if we modify our setup and make the system lighter and detachable to allow working with the complex apex configurations. This will be achieved by using light floats (e.g. commercial carbon-made boats), Fig. 1c. These modifications will also require manufacturing of the joints for connecting the hulls of the boats that can be detached quickly when necessary.

For the construction of the experimental facilities, we need raw materials. The list of materials and estimates of their costs are presented in Table 1. The manufacturing of box-cages will be carried out with the support of technical personnel at IGB. The measuring platform will be manufactured by the technicians of IGB; however, some elements of the construction will require production by third party workshops (welding of aluminum, milling of leveling screws).

Figure 1. (a) Schematic view of field experimental facilities for wake studies, (b) a view of the setup in previous field experiments on the Tagliamento river (after *Sukhodolov & Sukhodolova* 2016), and (c) a cross-sectional view of a measuring setup for the proposed study of wake flows.

Annex 4. Documentary “When Rivers Meet” (Public Relations Module)

The film will start with the view of the confluence of the Alakhanda and Bha-girathi Rivers in India, at the apex of which the Ganges River is believed to begin (Fig. 1). The Ganges is the most sacred river to Hindus and a very diverse ecosystem with about 140 species of fish. Raghunathji Temple is located at the confluence, which the place where Rama had first performed penance according to a legend. This temple is a prominent pilgrimage center. The stagnation zone of the confluence serves as the sacred bath for pilgrims.

Fig. 1 (a) The view of the confluence (turbid waters are from the Alakhanda side). (b) The view of the confluence apex and the temple from the downstream during the phase of intensive jetting on from the Bhagirathi. (c) Religious festival on the Ganges River. (d) Pilgrims performing penance at the confluence apex.

When two rivers differing in turbidity meet, they make the impression of purification when somebody steps into turbid (dirty) water and exits from transparent water (clean). This symbolizes purification, or the rationale of penance.

Next, the film will continue with an example from Germany – the confluence of the Rhein and Mosel Rivers at Koblenz – the Deutsches Eck (Fig. 2). This confluence has long been a symbol of unification of Germany which was signified by the erection of a monument to Kaiser Wilhelm I, who led the three wars that led to unification of separate German-speaking states. The monument is supplied with blocks of the Berlin Wall.

Fig. 2 (a) The view of the confluence (turbid waters are from the Rhein side). (b) The view of the confluence apex from upstream. (c) Submerged confluence apex during high flood.

When two streams collide at a confluence, they can either mix rapidly or flow adjacent to each other and share the riverbed with little mixing. This confluence mixing metaphor fully applies to nations.

The reference to Berlin brings us to the recent mass kill of fish on the Oder River. We show that there is a case of very slow mixing of joining rivers, as shown at the confluence of the Oder and Warthe Rivers (Fig. 3a). Dr. Christian Wolter will be interviewed about this problem. This will provide background for how confluences influence industrial use of rivers and their long-neglected problem of loss of biodiversity.

Fig. 3 (a) The view of the confluence (turbid waters are from the Oder side). (b) Dead fish in the Oder. (c) Dr. Christian Wolter introducing the study.

Both fast and slow mixing can have their strong and weak sides, which humans need to know to regulate better natural rivers to serve sustainably. There is a tendency to adopt strict engineering methods to control sediment, nutrient, and pollutant fluxes to regulate rivers.

This loss of biodiversity can be illustrated with the fluxes of transport at highway junctions and the associated problems of “back flows” – the development of traffic jams, stagnation at the junction apex, acceleration and recovery of transport capacities that have strong similarities with confluence dynamics in rivers (Fig. 4). We will show the Los Angeles River, which is a “monument” of industrialized river landscapes. In both junction flows of automobiles and regulated rivers there is a similar passenger – humans in the cars and fish in habitat of the confluent streams.

Fig. 4 Views of traffic jams at highway junctions (a) the view in the direction of motion and (b) upstream of the car fluxes. (c) Confluence along the Los Angeles River.

Engineering involves a centralized design associated with a schematization and specific rules that supposed to function well under certain conditions. The drawback is that centralized systems can easily fail if the systems behave chaotically. Even in such complex systems the mechanisms of self-organization can generate a new state of order.

This brings the attention to the mechanisms that govern river mixing in natural rivers. One of prominent river systems in Europe is the Tagliamento River – The King of Alps and a fluvial ecosystem of European importance. International scientific attention and research on the Tagliamento has occurred over the last 25 years. Prof. Klement Tockner will present an interview about this research on the Tagliamento during the planned workshop (Fig. 5). He was for many years the director of this research.

Fig. 5 (a) A view of the confluence of the Tagliamento and Fella Rivers. (b) Fish feeding at the mixing interface with turbid and clean water. (c) Prof. Tockner at the bridge across the Tagliamento.

Natural rivers are unique self-organizing systems in the non-organic world. They are very resilient ecosystems capable of a high degree of adaptation to variable abiotic factors under the climate’s rapidly changing conditions.

After the introduction of the Tagliamento River research in general, there will be an interview about the RIVER-LAB experimental approach of IGB and an introduction to the current project (Fig. 6). This interview will be performed by Dr. Alexander Sukhodolov and will also include an introduction of the project co-investigators, personnel and their expertise. The team will be filmed during the workshop on the Tagliamento which will allow for organizing effective introduction to different aspects in a natural, discussion-based way.

Fig. 6 (a) The RIVER-LAB model of confluence mixing (b) Dr. Alexander Sukhodolov will introduce the RIVER-LAB methodology and facilities of IGB. (c) Experimental setup in the model of a confluence.

The RIVER-LAB is the research platform which allows the use of methods typically employed in the laboratory at the scale of natural environments. This avoids serious issues associated with the upscaling of results, which are typical of laboratory research. The RIVER-LAB allows for cross-disciplinary dialogue through the studies of fish-flow interactions.

The field studies will also involve application of many innovative techniques and devices such as unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) and underwater drones for observation of fish and for carrying out underwater videography (Fig. 7). Additionally, the modeling with eddy resolving techniques will allow for the use of computer animations as a tool to understand and quantify/compare the results of field experiments and computer simulations (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 (a) Using innovative techniques UAVs and underwater drones for fish observation. (b) Dr. Quinn Lewis operates a UAV during field survey. (c) Prof. G. Constantinescu explains the results of computer modeling.

In this project we will explore the synergy between field-based experiments, case studies in natural and regulated rivers, and advanced methods of theoretical and numerical modeling.

An important component of the proposed project that will be highlighted in the documentary is the study of incomplete mixing effects on fish ecology in the Oder River (Fig. 8). This will be made as a nested component of the ODER-SO special research program. It will include joint field activities of our teams and will provide many details on fish habitats and the importance of tributaries as spawning grounds. Because the recent mass kill of fish on the Oder River attracted great attention from the German government, it is likely that we will also film a discussion with important decision makers.

Fig. 8 (a) Fish sampling at the Oder River. (b) Dr. Wolter keeps records of fish surveys. (c) Dr. Wolter introduces the German minister of foreign affairs A. Baerbock to the problem of mass fish kill at this transboundary river.

Migrating salmon navigate by the “smell” of water at their spawning tributaries. This is an amazing mechanism where incomplete mixing is vital for survival of fish population.

Prof. Quinn Lewis from the University of Waterloo in Canada will introduce this important and interesting aspect of confluence mixing (Fig. 9a). This will also be expanded by providing information about the migratory sturgeon in the Oder River and a special program of IGB to recover the population of sturgeon. Dr. Jorn Gessner from IGB together with Dr. C. Wolter will inform about this program. Additionally, they will talk about the role of incomplete mixing, which helps fish survive during the spread of the toxic algae.

Fig. 9 (a) Prof. Q. Lewis talking about salmon run. (b) Underwater salmon video. (c) A spectacular shot of a salmon leap.

Interactions of merging flows at confluences can also directly impact society by locally increasing water levels and causing backwater effects that in some cases lead to inundation of cities.

At this point we will be approaching the discussion of obtained results of the proposed study and their use for interpretation of observations in other river confluences. We will provide the illustrations from experiments, analysis and upscaling. For example, we will show the confluence of the Danube with Inn and Ilz at Passau (Fig. 10). An additional increase in the water levels within this confluence apex is attributed to the interaction of merging flows and development of a wave, which we demonstrate in our experiments.

Fig. 10 (a) View of the confluence at Passau. (b) This confluence is unique in respect that this is a case when three rivers meet. (c) Due to strong interactions of merging flows the water levels during floods increase more than that in the rivers causing inundation of the city.

Rivers are the veins of our Planet. They are often used and abused, to the point that their natural functions are degraded. We need to raise the public awareness about their fragility and need for protection and restoration.

Here we will return again to the issue of impacts of human activities on rivers. To draw attention to the overuse of rivers as a recreational resource it is important to compare the Los Angeles River and the King of the Alps – the Tagliamento. Although at the beginning of the film we show the Tagliamento as the natural counter example, its present day use is not so much different in recreational sense.

Fig. 11 (a-b) A scene from the Hollywood film “Grease” filmed at the Los Angeles River (1978 with John Travolta). (c-d) A typical summer scene at the Tagliamento River, which became an Eldorado for off-road driving clubs from Italy, Germany, Austria, Netherlands, Poland and other EU states.

Although recreational activities certainly affect the river ecosystems, they are not comparable with the scales of pollution problems on the rivers. However, quite often these pollution problems are not so apparent.

Although pollution with harmful substances causes large momentary damages to fluvial ecosystems, pollution with plastic objects imposes less obvious but often long-term effects. Even the Ganges River, which is sacred and worshiped, has become the world’s largest source of microplastic to the ocean (Fig. 12). Rivers often considered pristine, such as the Tagliamento, are also experiencing pollution – which may be even worse than in highly regulated rivers. There is a strong need to inform and to involve the public in general with practical measures to prevent such problems.

Fig. 12 (a) Plastic pollution on the Ganges River. (b) Transport of plastic in the river water. (c) Accumulation of plastic in the patches of riparian vegetation on the Tagliamento River.

The film will end with a demonstration of how citizen science guided by professional scientists can help to prevent and reduce the problems of pollution in rivers. This is also important to inform the public in general, and the proposed documentary is expected to attract considerable attention.

This documentary will be produced by Dr. Alexander Sukhodolov in cooperation with Mr. Eugenio Novajra and Prof. Quinn Lewis. Particularly important will be involvement of Mr. Novajra for the following producing: (1) the part about confluence of Ganges and its pollution problems; (2) to film rare hydrologic events (e.g. flooding) at the confluences of the Tagliamento River; and (3) to help filming the activities of RIVER-LAB. For production we will use mainly the footage which we will produce during the project and additionally footage that we can purchase from commercial stocks (e.g. the footage of Los Angeles River, salmon run footage). Financial support will be generally necessary for supporting travel.